

A Successful Case Study Emphasizing the Effectiveness of Ayurvedic Management in *Greevagraha*

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ABSTRACT

Greevagraha is one of the *Vatavyadhi* characterised by *Shoola* (Pain), *Suptata* (Numbness), *Dourbalyata* (Weakness), and *Chestahani* (Loss/Restricted range of movement). When *Kupitha Vata* gets embedded in *Greeva* causes *Greevagraha*. This can be established parallel to Cervical Spondylosis in the contemporary system of medicine. Cervical spondylosis occurs mostly in fifth decade of life. According to the Global Burden of Disease 2015, neck pain remains the leading cause of years lived with disability (YLD) and the fourth leading cause of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). **Materials and Methods** – A 56-year-old male patient came to our hospital with weakness in right lower limb along with circumduction gait developed over 3 years associated with numbness in right hand since 15 years. Here we are highlighting the case of *Greevagraha* which was managed by Ayurvedic Treatment where external procedures like *Abhyanga*, *Swedana*, *Basti*, and *Nasya* were given for 14 days, and internal medicines like *Gandharvahastadi Kashaya*, *Trayodashanga Guggulu*, and *Avipatti churna*, etc., were prescribed for 14 days. **Results and Discussion** – The Ayurvedic treatment approach has led to a notable improvement in the patient's condition and has also enhanced the range of motion in the affected limbs. **Conclusion** – The Ayurvedic treatment protocol has focused on restoring balance to the vitiated *Doshas*, thereby aiding in *Samprapti Vighatana* (disruption of the disease progression). The patient had significant improvement in reduction of his symptoms, enhanced confidence, and improved Quality of Life.

Keywords: *Greevagraha*, Cervical Spondylitis, Ayurvedic Treatment, Holistic Approach, *Vatavyadhi*.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurvedic principles are based on three *Doshas* Vata, Pitta, and Kapha, Vata being of utmost importance of all the three as it the only *Dosha* that is responsible for *Gati* (movement). *Vatavyadhi* are the group of diseases caused by to derangement of Vata *Dosha*. There are 80 *Nanatmaja Vata Vikara* ^[1] which consists of *Rukshata* of *Twacha*, *Padadari* (Cracked foot) to *Pakshaghata* (*Hemiplegia*). *Vatavyadhi* has a complex pathogenesis and can occur suddenly without any

Purvarupa ^[2]. Hence, its equilibrium and correction of deranged Vata *Dosha* plays an important role in *Chikitsa*. With absence of *Purvarupa* and a big impact with the slightest aggravation can lead to many diseases and sometimes can cause many symptoms which makes it difficult to land on one particular diagnosis.

Contemporary medicine has its limitations in managing these diseases. Their treatment mainly provides symptomatic relief which in the future leads

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to recurrence of the symptoms and exasperating side effects. A case of 56 years old male patient in distress from Vatavyadhi is being discussed here who has been managed with Ayurvedic treatment. Sthanika Chikitsa like Abhyanga, Swedana, Virechana, and Basti along with Abhyantara Chikitsa like Snehapana, Shamana Aushadhis were administered after assessing Roga Avastha and Rogi bala. Pathyaapathya was also strictly followed. These gave tremendous relief and symptoms diminished. This integrative approach of Ayurveda has demonstrated assuasive and encouraging results.

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1 Case report –A 56 years old male patient who is working as a Head of the Institute and Professor, came to our OPD with complaints of weakness in right lower limb along with feeling like slipping of the leg while walking which has progressed in to circumduction gait and feeling loss of balance while he climbs the stairs for the past 3 years. Due to this he is not confident walking without support of wall especially during climbing stairs and walks very slowly. This was associated with feeling of numbness in the right hand along with tremors in both the upper limbs which gradually developed over 15 years, with more intensity in recent years, which has resulted in difficulty in holding the chalk/marker for longer durations. His complaints worsen when he drives two-wheeler. He approached allopathic doctor 5 years ago with the complaints of numbness and tremors in hands, who has advised for MRI and impression showed degenerative changes in cervical region and the physician diagnosed it as cervical disc compression and advised him to undergo for surgery

but he was reluctant. He is a known case of Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus since 1year and was under medication (Glimepiride 500mg per – oral twice a day). Patient approached contemporary medicine for above complaints and was under medication for 2 years but discontinued after he felt his symptoms were progressing. As he expressed concern over weakness in right lower limb, we advised to undergo MRI of Whole Spine, which showed loss of cervical lordosis, compression in cervical region and he approached us for betterment of his condition.

Personal History—He was on a mixed diet and has a habit of drinking tea and coffee three times a day. His appetite is good, his bowels (Well-formed stools, once a day) and micturition (no burning or itching) is regular, and his sleep is sound.

On Examination – His Blood Pressure was 110/78mmHg, Pulse was of 89beats/m, Respiratory rate being 17cycles/min, SpO₂ of 98%, Afebrile (37°C) and has Pedal Edema on his left lower limb.

Systemic Examination –

1. Cardiovascular System – S1, S2 heard, no murmurs.
2. Respiratory System – NVBS, no breathlessness.
3. GI System – No organomegaly.
4. Central Nervous System – Central Nervous System and Higher Motor Functions intact.
5. Musculoskeletal System – Affected.

Table 1 – Range of Motion

Shoulder joint	Right	Left
1. Flexion	Normal	Normal
2. Extension	Normal	Normal
3. Abduction	Normal	Normal
4. Adduction	Normal	Normal
5. External Rotation	Normal	Normal
6. Internal Rotation	Normal	Normal
Hand	Right	Left
1. Palmar Flexion	Decreased and associated with numbness	Decreased and associated with numbness

2. Dorsi Flexion	Decreased and associated with numbness	Decreased and associated with numbness
Lower Limb	Right	Left
1. Flexion	Reduced	Normal
2. Extension	Reduced	Normal
3. Abduction	Able to perform but numbness positive	Normal
4. Adduction	Normal	Normal
5. External Rotation	Decreased and associated with numbness	Normal
6. Internal Rotation	Decreased and associated with numbness	Normal
Foot	Right	Left
1. Plantar Flexion	Decreased and associated with numbness	Normal
2. Dorsi Flexion	Decreased and associated with numbness	Normal

Ashtavidha Pareeksha

- Nadi –Pitta – Kaphaja
- Mutra – Prabhoota - Aphenayukta
- Mala – Nirama
- Jihwa – Lipta
- Shabda – Spashta
- Sparsha – Anushnasheeta
- Drik – Madhyama
- Aakriti – Madhyama
- Vikruti – Vata, Mamsa, Greeva, Dakshina bhaga Adhithana
- Sara – Rasa, Rakta
- Samhanana – Madhyama
- Pramana – Madhyama
- Satmya – Vyamisra leaning more towards Amla, Lavana, Madhura and Katu rasa
- Satva – Satva - Tama
- Vayah – Madhyama
- Ahara Shakti – Pravara
- Vyayama Shakti – Avara

Dashavidha Pareeksha

- Prakruti – Kapha-Vataja

Table 2 – MRI Cervical Spine Impression (04/03/2022):

Level	C2-C3	C3-C4	C4-C5	C5-C6	C6-C7
Cm	1.3	1.3	0.5	0.5	1.3

- Degenerative changes in the cervical spine in the form of multilevel disc desiccation, marginal osteophytes, and posterior longitudinal ligament thickening.
- At C4-C5 and C5-C6 central disc protrusion along with PLL thickening and osteophytes causes marked narrowing of the spinal canal and impingement of the cord with the cord signal changes at this level in keeping with myelomalacic changes.
- The neural foraminae are narrowed bilaterally with impingement of the exiting nerve roots.
- Degenerative changes in the form of marginal osteophytes. Disc desiccation, mild ligamentum flavum thickening, minimal facet effusion seen at multiple levels in cervical spine.
- Loss of Cervical Lordosis.
- Causing disc bulge at C₃ – C₄, C₅ – C₆ causing indentation on the ventral thecal sac, indentation on the cervical cord, mild narrowing of bilateral lateral recess, indentation of bilateral transversing and exiting nerve roots.
- Disc osteophyte complex with central protrusion seen at C₄ – C₅ level causing moderate narrowing of spinal cord, moderate narrowing of bilateral lateral recess, compression of cervical cord and bilateral transversing nerve roots, indentation of bilateral exiting nerve roots at this level.

Table 3 – Pathological investigations (02/07/23)

Fasting Blood Sugar	118mg/dl
Post-prandial Blood Sugar	216mg/dl
Total Cholesterol	168mg/dl
Triglycerides	200mg/dl

MRI Whole Spine Impression (05/07/23):**Table 4 – Timeline**

2008 - 2018	Patient developed numbness in the tip of fingers, but he ignored it. It gradually progressed to whole fingers which lead to difficulty in holding things.
2018	As the numbness had developed severely which was affecting his daily routine, he had approached allopathic physician with above symptoms for which they suggested for surgery but patient was reluctant to undergo.
2020	Patient developed weakness in right lower limb and felt like his leg is slipping while he is walking and developed circumduction gait.
2021	Patient approached allopathic physician and was under symptomatic treatment. He felt relieved at first. But later the symptoms reoccurred. So, he discontinued the medications.
2022	Patient had raised post-prandial blood sugar and was diagnosed as Diabetic and started Diabetic medication.
2023	As the complaints of weakness and tiredness with minimal amount of work increased, patient approached our OPD and on advice of admission, got admitted in our IPD.

After a detailed history, laboratory procedures, and examinations were done, even though the MRI showed Cervical root compression, the patient expressed that his lower limb complaints were more severe. After examination of the patient, we had various provisional diagnoses i.e., Kampavata (Parkinson's Disease), Pakshaghata (Stroke) which can be in its initial stages, Avarana of Vyana Vata,

Sarvanga Vatavyadhi, etc., As the patient presented with various complaints, we diagnosed the patient as under **Vatavyadhi** Spectrum mainly pertaining to **Greevagraha** (Neck pain) and formulated a treatment protocol in lines of **Samanya Vatavyadhi Chikitsa** [3], also mainly directing treatment procedures to reduce the cervical complaints. Our treatment was focused on balancing the Vata Dosha, imparting

strength to muscles, alleviation of numbness in upper limbs, and assistance in achieving normal gait.

2.2 Treatment Protocol:

Table 5 – Internal Medications

Dravya (Medicine)	Matra (Dosage)	Anupana (Medium)	Aushadha Sevana kala (Time of administration)
Gandharvahastadi kashaya	10ml (BD)	With 60ml of lukewarm water, twice daily.	On empty stomach
Maharasnadi Kashaya	10ml (BD)		
Trayodashanga Guggulu	1-0-1	With kashaya	On empty stomach
Ashwagandha churna	½ tsp – 0 – ½ tsp	With warm milk	After food
Avipatti churna	0 – 0 – 1tsp	With warm water	At bedtime

Table 6 – External Procedures

Dates	Procedure
6/7/23 to 8/7/23	Dhanyamala Dhara. Nasya with Karpasasthyadi Taila 2 drops in each nostril, morning and evening. 10 sets of upper and lower limb exercises were done.
9/7/23 to 13/7/23	Abhyanga with Karpasasthyadi Taila. Patra Pinda Sweda. Nasya with Karpasasthyadi Taila 2 drops in each nostril, morning and evening. Matravasti with Pippalyadi Taila. Exercises of Upper limb and Lower limb which were gradually increased from 10 sets to 20 sets morning and evening.
14/7/23	Sadyovirechana with 40ml Gandharvashasti Eranda Taila where he had 9 vegas.
15/7/23	1-day Samsarjana Krama.
16/7/23 to 20/7/23	Abhyanga with Karpasasthyadi Taila. Shastika Shali Pinda Sweda. Nasya with Karpasasthyadi Taila 2 drops in each nostril, morning and evening. Upper and Lower limb exercises maintained at 20 sets morning and evening.
20/7/23	Patient got discharged after procedures and was advised to come for follow up after 14 days.

Table 7 – Internal Medications advised during discharge

Dravya (Medicine)	Matra (Dosage)	Anupana (Medium)	Aushadha Sevana kala (Time of administration)
Maharasnadi Kashaya	10 ml	Mixed with 40 ml of lukewarm water	On empty stomach
Guggulutiktaka Kashaya	10 ml		
Trayodashanga Guggulu	2 – 0 – 2	With Kashaya	On empty stomach

Ashwagandhadi Churnam	1tsp – 0 – 1tsp	With warm milk	After food
Balaashwagandhadi Taila	Q. S	Heat it indirectly on double boiler till it becomes lukewarm and massage on body	30mins – 1 hr before bath
Sahacharadi Taila	Q. S		

1. RESULTS:

Table 8 – Examinations

Examination	Before Treatment		After Treatment	
	Right	Left	Right	Left
SLR	40 degrees	55 degrees	80 degrees	90 degrees
Braggard's	Positive	Positive	Negative	Negative
Slump Test	Positive	Positive	Positive	Negative
FABER'S Test	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative
Femoral Nerve Test	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative
Spurling's Test	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative
Arm Squeeze Test	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative

Table 9 – Range of Motion

Shoulder	Before Treatment		After Treatment	
	Right	Left	Right	Left
1. Flexion	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
2. Extension	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
3. Abduction	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
4. Adduction	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
5. External Rotation	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
6. Internal Rotation	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
Hand	Before Treatment		After Treatment	
	Right	Left	Right	Left
1. Palmar Flexion	Decreased and associated with numbness	Decreased and associated with numbness	Numbness Redcued	Numbness Reduced
2. Dorsi Flexion	Decreased and associated with numbness	Decreased and associated with numbness	Normal	Normal
Lower Limb	Before Treatment		After Treatment	

	Right	Left	Right	Left
1. Flexion	Reduced	Normal	Normal	Normal
2. Extension	Reduced	Normal	Normal	Normal
3. Abduction	Able to perform but numbness positive	Normal	Numbness Reduced	Normal
4. Adduction	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
5. External Rotation	Decreased and associated with numbness	Normal	Numbness Reduced	Normal
6. Internal Rotation	Decreased and associated with numbness	Normal	Numbness Reduced	Normal
Foot	Before Treatment		After Treatment	
	Right	Left	Right	Left
1. Plantar Flexion	Decreased and associated with numbness	Normal	Numbness reduced	Normal
2. Dorsi Flexion	Decreased and associated with numbness	Normal	Numbness reduced	Normal

Table 10 – Reflexes

Deep Reflexes	Before Treatment		After Treatment	
	Right	Left	Right	Left
Biceps	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
Triceps	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
Knee Jerk	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
Babinski sign	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal

Table 11 – Lower-Spine Examinations

Test	Before Treatment	After Treatment
Flip Coin Test	Normal	Normal
Distraction Test	No change in numbness of the Fingers	Normal
Schober's Test	Normal	Normal
Glabellar Tap	Normal	Normal
Whole Spine Tenderness	Grade 0 (No tenderness)	No Tenderness
Jaw Jerk	Normal	Normal
Abdominal Reflex	Normal	Normal

Table 12 – Measurements

Circumference	Before Treatment		After Treatment	
	Right	Left	Right	Left
Arm	34cm	35cm	35.5cm	36cm
Forearm	27cm	27cm	27cm	27cm
Thigh	45.5cm	44.5cm	45.5cm	44.5cm
Calf	40cm	41cm	41cm	41cm

- During Dhanyamla Dhara, the patient initially had stiffness, later on the 3rd day he felt that his stiffness reduced and his pedal Edema also reduced significantly by the 3rd day.
- After Abhyanga and Patra Pinda Sweda, the patient felt his weakness in the lower limbs reduced and the circumduction gait gradually reduced.
- After Sadyo Virechana, the patient felt lightness of the body and his appetite increased.
- After Matravasti, further weakness in his lower limbs and numbness in right hand reduced. He also assured that he is not feeling

the slipping of his leg while walking. His gait changed to normal and he feels more confident to walk fast and without any assistance.

4. DISCUSSION:

4.1 Nidana Panchaka:

Nidana – Intake of more Amla, Lavana, Madhura, Katu rasa, Nature of his work – Standing for more hours, looking upward to board, Writing on the board for longer durations.

Rupa – Dourbalyata in right leg, fingers of right hand, Greevagraha.

Samprapti –

Figure 1 – Flowchart showing Samprapti**Samprapti Ghataka –**

- Dosha – Vata, Kapha
- Dushya – Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Asthi
- Adhithana – Greeva, Dakshina Hasta, Pada
- Srotas – Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Mamsavaha, Asthivaha
- Srotodushti – Sanga, Vimarga Gamana
- Agni – Vishamagni
- Vyadhi Sambhava – Naveena – Mridu; Jeerna – Daruna
- Rogamarga – Madhyama Rogamarga

4.2 Mode of Action of Dhanyamla Dhara –

Dhanyamla Dhara^[4] is a type of Drava Sweda among Chatursweda, where the liquid from Dhanya is fermented and used for Ekanga or Sarvanga Sweda. It is Ushna Veerya. It also mitigates Kapha and Vata. It does Srotoshodhana, hence aids in Amajanya Vikara. It also can be applied in Vatavyadhi because of its Vatanulomana, Shula Prashamana properties. It is also widely recognised for its efficacy in enhancing strength, nutrition which is executed by instant action, infiltration into deeper tissues and elimination of blockage, inturn assisting in circulation, lightness in the body, restoring normalcy of health and halting advancement of the condition.

1.3 Mode of Action of Abhyanga –

Abhyanga^[5] is massage of the whole body which alleviates stress, stiffness and helps in circulation of the blood. It imparts Bala, Susparsha, Dridhatva to the body. And Nasya is administration of the drug into nostrils which through olfactory route enters into circulation and passes through Blood- Brain Barrier and helps in distribution of the medicine to brain. This

helps in expulsion of the Doshas through nose and ensuring smooth functioning of brain^[6].

Karpasasthyadi Taila^[7] has been indicated for different mode of administration like Abhyanga, Nasya, Vasti etc., Karpasasthyadi Taila has Karpasa, Pippalimoola, Masha, Kulattha etc., These have Snigdha guna, Ushna Veerya, Vata – Kapha hara karma, Vedana-sthapana, Shotha Hara properties. Due to these properties, it has been indicated in Vatavyadhi. Gossypin, a flavonoid found in Karpasa Beeja has demonstrated various pharmacological activities including antinociceptive activity which inhibits Prostaglandins, further aiding in reduction of pain and swelling. Hence, was espoused for both Abhyanga and Nasya.

4.4 Mode of Action of Patra Pinda Sweda –

Patra Pinda Sweda^[8] is a procedure where the leaves of the drugs are tied into a bundle. Most of the Patras like Eranda Patra, Nirgundi Patra etc., are used and possess Vata-Kaphahara property. They also facilitate Srotoshodhana, hence imparting lightness of the body and relieving any stiffness. This procedure also helps in circulation of the blood.

4.5 Mode of Action of Matravasti –

Matravasti – “Vasti Vataharaanam Sreshtam” has been mentioned by Acharya Charaka. He also explained Vasti as Ardhachikitsa. Vastidravaya enters the Pakvashaya which the main site of Vata Dosha and expels it out through its Veerya. When Vastidravaya is expelled out, it also takes Vata Dosha and promote Vatanulomana, inturn enhancing Jataragni. It also acts on Pitta and Kapha Dosha and brings them into balanced state and provides strength. The Matravasti is promotive of strength without any demand of strict regimen of diet, causes easy elimination of Mala and Mutra. It performs the function of Brimhana and cures Vatavyadhi^[9].

Pippalyadi Taila^[10] has Pippali, Madhuka, Shati, Bilwa, Vacha, Godugdha etc., It is indicated in

Arshas, Mudhavata, Katigraha, Prishtagraha, Dourbalya. The drugs also have anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties. Hence, was opted for Matravasti.

4.6 Mode of Action of Sadyo Virechana –

Sadyovirechana is a procedure where Virechana is done when Doshas are in Utklesha Avastha and can be expelled without foregoing Snehanapana. Here, Gandharvahastadi Eranda Taila has been preferred for its Vatanulomana and Koshta Shodana Karma. It also facilitates in Sneha Virechana which has been advised in regimen of Vataja Rogas. With these into consideration 40ml of Gandharvahastadi Eranda Taila [11] has been prescribed.

4.7 Mode of Action of Shastika Shali Pinda Sweda –

Shastika Shali Pinda Sweda is a type of Sankara Sweda procedure where Sastika type of rice is cooked in milk and Balamoola Kashaya, then made into bolus and tied and used for massage over the body. Shastika Shali is Madhura rasa, Sheeta Veerya, Shareera Drdhyakrit. Balamoola has Balya, Vatahara properties. The bolus dipped in Balamoola Kashaya and used for massage aids in circulation, assists in reduction of stiffness. Hence, it assists in reduction of pain and promotes circulation and imparts strength to the muscles [12]. Shastika Shali Pinda Sweda has shown remarkable improvements in Musculo-skeletal diseases like Generalised weakness, degenerative joint disorders, Hemiplegia, Cerebral Palsy, Muscular dystrophy etc.,

Table 13 – Mode Of Action of Internal Medicines.

Medication	Properties
Gandharvahastadi Kashaya	It has Vata-Kapha hara, Anulomana property. Most of the drugs have anti-inflammatory properties [13].
Maharasnadi Kashaya	It inhods Vata -Kapha hara, Srotoshodana, Vatanulomana action. Most of the drugs possess anti-inflammatory property, analgesic properties [14].
Ashwagandhadi Churna	It has Vata-kapha shamaka, Balya property. This helps in reduction of Vata and increases strength of the body [15].
Avipatti Churna	The drugs have Deepana, Kapha-Vata hara, Shoolahara properties. They also have Anti- inflammatory, analgesic, antioxidant and gastro-protective action [16].
Trayodashanga Guggulu	They possess Vatahara, Vedana shamana property. They have also demonstrated anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antioxidant property [17].
Guggulu Tiktaka Kashaya	It has Nimba, Patola, Vasa, Vidanga, Guggulu etc., It has been indicated in Kushta, Sandhigata, Ashtigata, Majjagata Vata [18].
Balaashwagandhadi Taila	Bala and Ashwagandha are well known for their Vatahara, Balya property which aids in imparting strength and can be utilised in all kinds of Vatavyadhi [19].
Sahacharadi Taila	The ingredients of this Taila possess Madhura rasa, Madhura Vipaka, Ushna Veerya. In Astanga Hridaya it is explained as “ Siddham Kricchraan Sheelitam Hanti Vaatan ”, which rapidly helps in bringing normalcy to Vata Dosha. Due to these properties, it benefits in reduction of Vata and exemplify as Brimhana, imparting nourishment and strength [20].

5. CONCLUSION –

Equilibrium state of Dosha, Dhatu, Mala contributes in maintenance of health of an individual and Vatadosha is responsible for Gati of Dosha, Dhatu and

Mala. It also regulates all the body functions. Vatadosha when in normalcy aids in preservation of whole body and its subtypes Prana, Udana, Vyana, Samana and Apana. On contrary, when Vata is vitiated, it causes enormous diseases and also

diminishes **Bala** (Strength), **Varna** (Complex), **Sukha** (Pleasure/happiness), **Ayu** (lifespan) and also affects the normal bodily functions. Thus, critical understanding of disease pathogenesis, manifestation, predisposing factors, treatment protocol etc., are crucial for clinical achievements. Acharya Charaka has mentioned in detail about Abhyantara Snehana, Bahya Snehana, Swedana, Basti karma etc., in Chikitsa of Vatavyadhi. Along with Samshodhana, Samshamana aushadhis were advised to patient and he strictly adhered to Pathyaapathya advised to him. Following these, patient had substantial improvement. His complaints were diminished during the course of treatment and had boost to his confidence and mental well-being. The results were assuasive and enhanced his Quality of Life.

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5.2 Conflict of Interest – None declared.

REFERENCES

1. Sharma.P.V, Caraka Samhita, Agnivesa's treatise refined and annotated by Caraka and redacted by Drdhabala, Text with English translation, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, Vol. I, Ed:2014, Sutra Sthana, Chapter 20, Shloka 12.
2. Sharma.P.V, Caraka Samhita, Agnivesa's treatise refined and annotated by Caraka and redacted by Drdhabala, Text with English translation, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, Vol. II, Ed:2014, Chikitsa Sthana, Chapter 28, Shloka 58-60.
3. Sharma.P.V, Caraka Samhita, Agnivesa's treatise refined and annotated by Caraka and redacted by Drdhabala, Text with English translation, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, Vol. II, Ed:2014, Chikitsa Sthana, Chapter 28, Shloka 75-80.
4. Vandana, Alok Kumar Srivastava, Meenakshi Gusain, Priyanka. Efficacy of Dhanyamla Sarvanga Dhara in the Management of Obesity: An Analytical Review. International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research. 2018;6(6):81-84.
<https://ijapr.in/index.php/ijapr/article/view/987>
5. Sharma.P.V, Caraka Samhita, Agnivesa's treatise refined and annotated by Caraka and redacted by Drdhabala, Text with English translation, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, Vol. I, Ed:2014, Sutra Sthana, Chapter 5.
6. Vipin Kumar. A Conceptual Study on Mode of Action of Nasya. International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research, 2017;5(7):100-102.
<https://ijapr.in/index.php/ijapr/article/view/728>
7. Nidhee Thakur, Pushpinder Singh, Charu Supriya. A Clinical Study to Evaluate the Combined Effect of Karpasasthyadi Taila Nasya and Greevabasti in the Management of Greevastambha w.s.r. to Cervical Spondylosis. International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research. 2022;10(Suppl 2):18-23.
<https://doi.org/10.47070/ijapr.v10iSuppl2.2556>
8. Kumar S. CONCEPTUAL REVIEW ON PATRA PINDA POTTALI SWEDA: AN AYURVEDIC THERAPEUTIC APPROACH. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research; 2025(VOLUME 11, FEBRUARY ISSUE 2). Available from: https://www.wjpmr.com/home/article_abstract/6256
9. Shah MR, Mehta CS, Shukla VD, Dave AR, Bhatt NN. A Clinical study of Matra Vasti and an ayurvedic indigenous compound drug in the management of Sandhigatavata (Osteoarthritis). Ayu. 2010 Apr;31(2):210-7. doi: 10.4103/0974-8520.72399.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3215366/>
10. Rijin Rajeev, Mohammad Sadique, Karthikeya Prasad. Comparative Clinical Evaluation of Matra Basti with Pippalyadi Taila and Ashtakatvara Taila in Katishoola. International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research. 2022;10(10):35-43. <https://doi.org/10.47070/ijapr.v10i10.2571>
11. Lavanya U, G. S. Hadimani, Akshay R. Shetty. A Randomised Comparative Clinical Study to Evaluate the Efficacy of Sadhyovirechana with Gandharvahastadi Eranda Taila followed by Agnilepa and Dhanyamla Dhara in the Management of Amavata. AYUSHDHARA, 2023;10(6):12-19. Available from: <https://ayushdhara.in/index.php/ayushdhara/article/view/1436>
12. Pratima Yadav and Ajay Kumar. Efficacy of Shastika Shali Pinda Sweda in Muscular Dystrophy: A Case Study. Int. J. Res. Ayurveda

- Pharm. 2021;12(4):12-14
<http://dx.doi.org/10.7897/2277-4343.120497>
13. Shahina Mole.S, Ammu.K.Sasi. A Case Study on Ayurvedic Management in PCOS. International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research. 2021;9(11):80-82.
<https://ijapr.in/index.php/ijapr/article/view/2111>
14. Rohan Mohandas, Muttappa Totad, Vasantha B, Sphoorthi Narasimhan. An open label single arm prospective clinical study in the management of Pakshaghata (CVA due to infarct) with Maharasnadi Kashaya and Shunti Churna. J Ayurveda Integr Med Sci 2020; 5:59-64.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.21760/jaims.5.5.7>
15. Krishnamurthy. M.S, Sahasrayogam, With Dharakalpa, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 2021, p.655.
16. Subha K Nampoothiri, A Shahul Hameed. A Critical Review on Avipathi Choorna- A Unique Formulation for Peptic Ulcer Disease. International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research. 2021;9(9):80-85.
<https://doi.org/10.47070/ijapr.v9i9.2038>
17. Shivani Gupta, Yadu Nandan Dey, Pushpendra Kannoja, Amit Kumar Halder, Deepti Sharma, Manish M. Wanjari, Shridhar Chougule, Sharad Pawar, Atul Kaushik, Sudesh N. Gaidhani, Shailendra Gurav, Analgesic and Anti-inflammatory Activities of Trayodashang Guggulu, an Ayurvedic Formulation, Phytomedicine Plus, Volume 2, Issue 3, 2022, 100281,ISSN 2667-0313,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phyplu.2022.100281>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2667031322000641>)
18. Girija PV, Renuka NK, Vijayan KK, Terpenoids in Gulguluthikthakam Kashayam: An ayurvedic formulation, Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry 2022; 11(2): 33-45. Available from:
<https://www.phytojournal.com/archives/2022.v11.i2.14373/terpenoids-in-gulguluthikthakam-kashayam-an-ayurvedic-formulation>
19. Krishnamurthy. M.S, Sahasrayogam, With Dharakalpa, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 2021, p.500.
20. Krishnamurthy. M.S, Sahasrayogam, With Dharakalpa, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 2021, p.464.

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